

LONG-TERM EXPOSURE OF POLYCYANATE COMPOSITES TO HIGH TEMPERATURE ATMOSPHERE

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1 Introduction

High performance polymeric composites have been applied to airframe structure due to their high-specific strength and high-specific stiffness. In accordance with requirements of speed and altitude of an supersonic aircraft, it is estimated that airframe surface is heated to 180 °C or more by aerodynamic heating. In addition, like a structure of a fighter aircraft which carries the engine in a fuselage, the airframe is exposed to high temperature by radiation and heat transfer from the engine. Because of being subjected to a static heat loading of several thousand hours or more during operation, an evaluation of thermo oxidative stability for polymer matrix composites (PMCs) is important. In order to evaluate the long-term stability of PMCs in high temperature environment, long-term exposure test to various high temperature atmospheres have been conducted, because the long-term performance of PMCs at elevated temperature is dictated by thermal and oxidative stability of the materials. Therefore, many PMCs have been tested on exposure tests at high temperatures including polyimide [1] and bismaleimide [2] matrix composites. These resins have a high glass transition temperature (T_g), thus they could endure under high temperature environment. Therefore, maximum temperature of the cure cycle of both polyimide and bismaleimide is higher than that of conventional epoxy resin. If using these high T_g resin, manufacturers might need a new autoclave to make structural components. For high temperature environment usage, curable resin using an existing autoclave is useful for airframe structural usage. Now we focus on other PMCs, polycyanate ester matrix composites, for aircraft main structural usage of an aircraft. The polycyanate resin has good processability similar to conventional epoxy resin, while the T_g is higher than that of epoxy. Furthermore the advantage of polycyanate resin is low moisture absorption characteristic. Therefore the

strength reduction due to moisture absorption in a high-temperature environment is small. Residual open-hole strength due to thermo-oxidative degradation is an important parameter for aircraft static strength design. The main purpose of this study was to evaluate effects of long-term exposure to high temperature air on the compressive strength for un-notched and notched, and on the tensile strength with notch of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) with polycyanate ester.

2 Test specimens and experimental condition

Figure 1 shows the geometry of test specimens. Test specimens were manufactured with polycyanate resin based prepreg system. Reinforcement of the prepreg was T700SC carbon fiber. The volume fraction of the specimens was approximately 0.56. The stacking sequence both non-hole compressive (NHC) test specimen and open-hole compressive (OHC) test specimen were [45/0/-45/90]_{3S}, while that of the open-hole tensile (OHT) test specimen was [45/0/-45/90]_{2S}. Each test of NHC, OHC and OHT was performed in compliance with ASTM D 6641, ASTM D6484, and ASTM D 5766. Before aging, all of the specimens were dried at 110 °C under 0.1 atm for 48 hours to remove moisture and volatile components. After drying, the specimens were cooled to room temperature. Initial weights were measured for all specimens before aging. The OHC and OHT specimens were exposed at 180 °C in air circulating ovens, while the NHC test specimens were exposed to 180 °C and 195 °C. These specimens were aged up to 1000 hours, with the exception of OHT test specimens which were exposed up to 1800 hours. During exposure period, the weight was measured periodically. Resolution of weight measurement is 1mg. When predefined exposure times had elapsed, tension/compression tests were conducted. Strength test of NHC and

OHT conducted at room temperature. Only OHC tests were conducted at 180 °C because of the most severe case. Test speed was 1mm/min. Three specimens were tested for each condition [3].

Fig. 1. Shape of test specimens.

Table 1. Exposure condition at each strength test.

Exposure condition	The number of specimen for each strength test condition	
	at RT*	at 180 °C
NHC Non-aged	3	-
NHC 100 hours aged at 180 °C	3	-
NHC 1000 hours aged at 180 °C	3	-
NHC 100 hours aged at 195 °C	3	-
NHC 1000 hours aged at 195 °C	3	-
OHC Non-aged	-	3
OHC 1000 hours aged at 180 °C	-	3
OHT Non-aged	3	-
OHT 1800 hours aged at 180 °C	3	-

*RT means room temperature.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Weight change

Figure 2 shows the comparison of the % weight loss of polycyanate composite specimens for the thermally aged at 180 °C and 195 °C. As expected, the weight loss at 195 °C was more larger than that of 180 °C. Figure 3 shows the comparison of the % weight loss for NHC, OHC, and OHT test specimens at 180 °C. During the first exposure period for OHT test specimens, % weight increased slightly. It had been reported that the weight of some epoxy laminate systems increase during initial aging period [4]. It is due to two competing reactions such as oxygen uptake which leads to weight gain and chain scission.

Fig. 2. Comparison of % weight loss between 180 °C and 195 °C for NHC.

Fig. 3. Comparison of % weight loss for each specimen at 180 °C.

3.2 NHC test

The NHC strength tests were studied at room temperature after aging at 180 °C and 195 °C for 0, 100 or 1000 hours. Figure 4 shows stress-strain curve that compares 0 (non-aged) to 1000 hours at 180 °C. No difference was observed for initial Young's modulus. Young's modulus for non-aged was 44.9GPa, and the other one for 1000 hours was 43.5GPa. Figure 5 shows stress-strain curve that compares 0 (non-aged) to 1000 hours at 195 °C. In the case of 195 °C, Young's modulus was same tendency comparing to no-aged and 195 °C. Young's modulus for 195 °C and 1000 hours aging was 43.0GPa. On Young's modulus, there is little effect of thermal exposure until 1000 hours. Figures 6 and 7 show stress - strain curve that show the region less than - 400MPa for each Figs. 4 and 5. Respectively load decrease was appeared before final failure of specimens. Figure 8 shows the effects of aging period and temperature on the stress of the first load decrease point. These load decrease were generated by some damages such as matrix crack or small fracture of specimen. The stress of the first load decrease point for all aging periods, at both 180 °C and 195 °C were increased by approximately 4 to 8 %. Figure 9 shows the effects of aging period and temperature on NHC strength. Compressive strength of specimens for all aging periods, at both 180 °C and 195 °C increased by approximately 4 to 6 %. Same tendency was observed on percent strength increase and percent stress increase of the first load decrease point. This would be caused by post curing effect of matrix. Compressive strength had increased within the first 100 hours for these exposure conditions, and did not change up to 1000 hours for these exposure temperatures. Figure 10 shows the failure mode that was not changed with aging time and exposure temperature. Failure mode of all exposure condition for NHC test was kinking in middle of gage section.

Fig. 4. Stress-strain curve that compares 0 (non-aged) to 1000 hours at 180 °C for NHC. [3]

Fig. 5. Stress-strain curve that compares 0 (non-aged) to 1000 hours at 195 °C for NHC. [3]

Fig. 6. Stress-strain curve less than -400MPa that compares 0 (non-aged) to 1000 hours at 180 °C for NHC. [3]

Fig. 7. Stress-strain curve less than -400MPa that compares 0 (non-aged) to 1000 hours at 195 °C for NHC. [3]

(a) Non-aged

(b) 180 °C, 1000 hours aged

(c) 195 °C, 1000 hours aged

Fig. 8. Stress of the first load decrease point for NHC. [3]

Fig. 9. NHC strength. [3]

Fig. 10. Polycyanate specimens after NHC test, in non-aged state and after 1000 hours aging at 180 °C and 195 °C.

3.3 OHC test

Figure 11 shows stress-strain curves for OHC at 180 °C comparing non-aged with 1000 hours aged. The strength test temperature was 180 °C. Due to strain measurement, an extensometer (Model 632.11F-20; MTS Systems Corporation) was placed around hole of specimen. In order to obtain stress value, load was divided by net-section area around hole. Similar to NHC, there was little effect for stiffness by thermal exposure. Before final failure, no sign such as load decrease was observed. Figure 12 Shows OHC strength also increased approximately 5 % by thermal exposure at 180 °C. About the standard deviation of strength, the value that were aged at 180 °C and 1000 hours exposure were smaller than that of non-aged. Figure 13 shows the failure mode that was not changed with aging time and exposure temperature. Failure mode of all exposure condition for OHC test was laterally compressive failure across the center of the hole.

Fig. 11. Stress-strain curve that compares 0 (non-aged) to 1000 hours at 180 °C for OHC. [3]

Fig. 12. OHC strength. [3]

(a) Non-aged

(b) 180 °C, 1000 hours aged

Fig. 13. Polycyanate specimens after OHC test, in (a) non-aged state and (b) after 1000 hours aging at 180 °C.

3.4 OHT test

Figure 14 shows stress-strain curves for OHC comparing non-aged with 1800 hours aged. The tests were conducted at room temperature. Strain measurement was conducted in the same manner as OHC. Similarly as NHC and OHC, there was little effect on stiffness by thermal exposure. Before final failure, there was a sign such as load decrease, but there was no difference in stress of the first load decrease point between non-aged and 1800 hours. Figure 15 shows OHT strength of specimens without aging and with aging 1800 hours at 180 °C. The tensile strength declined approximately 3 % in 1800 hours. It appears that the tensile strength had been decreased by the thermal exposure effects. About the standard deviation of strength, the value that was aged at 180 °C and 1800 hours exposure were smaller than that of non-aged. Figure 16 shows the failure mode that was not changed with aging time and exposure temperature. Failure mode of all exposure condition for OHT test was tension failure of 0° ply at the hole section with sublaminates splitting.

Fig. 14. Stress-strain curve that compares 0 (non-aged) to 1800 hours at 180 °C for OHT. [3]

Fig. 15. OHT strength. [3]

(a) Non-aged

(b) 180 °C, 1800 hours aged

Fig. 16. Polycyanate specimens after OHT test, in non-aged state and after 1800 hours aging at 180 °C.

3.5 Microscopic observation

After 1000 hours exposure, the specimen color became brownish tinge. This might be attributed to change in the resin of composites. Surface of 1000 hours aged specimen became rougher which was perceived by the sense of touch. Figure 17 and 18 show microscopic image of surface view of NHT specimens for various exposure conditions. Resin shrinkage and disappearance appeared with increasing exposure time. After 1000 hours exposure, matrix crack appeared along the fiber direction near the fiber. The specimens exposed at 195 °C (Fig. 18 (e)) were more severely damaged than those of 180 °C. Figure 19 shows microscopic images of side view of OHT specimens. Figure 19 (a) is non-aged specimen. Intra-laminar cracks, delamination and transverse cracks appeared. On the other hand, Fig. 19 (b) shows many transverse cracks in the 90° layers of the specimen exposed for 1800 hours. Figure 19 (c) shows an enlargement of Fig. 19 (b), in

the $\pm 45^\circ$ layer adjacent to 90° layers, matrix cracks were propagated from 90° layers and deflected. In 1000 hours aged specimens for NHC and OHC tests, matrix cracks in the 90° layers were also appeared similarly. This matrix cracks might not as a result of applied load. Earlier studies on PMR-15/Carbon [2] have shown that the material exhibit substantial degradation at high temperature in isothermal aging. The study showed that anisotropic behavior of composite degradation. Degradation occurs at a faster rate in cross section that perpendicular to the fiber direction than surface along fiber direction. As shown in Fig. 16 (b), matrix crack was occurred in 90° layers. So, thermal oxidative degradation was more severe in 90° layers than the other layers. This result was same as other PMCs research [1, 2, 4]. Matrix crack length along fiber direction was unknown in this study. But other research showed that the crack length was several hundred micrometers at most for several thousand exposure hours with carbon fiber reinforced polyimide at 177°C exposure [5]. As a result of this study, the matrix crack has little effect on young's modulus, compressive strength and even tensile strength. However, it seems that the fracture toughness of the polycyanate resin and/or the fiber-resin interfacial strength would be degraded by thermal exposure.

(a) Non-aged

Fig. 17. Microscopic image of surface view of NHT specimen for non-aged.

(b) 180°C , 100 hours aged

(c) 180°C , 1000 hours aged

(d) 195°C , 100 hours aged

(e) 195°C , 1000 hours aged

Fig. 18. Microscopic image of surface view of NHT specimens for various exposure conditions.

(a) Non-aged

(b) 1800 hours aged

(c) Crack deflection

Fig. 19. Microscopic images of side view of OHT specimens for non-aged and after 1800 hours aged.

4 Conclusions

We studied degradation of polycyanate-based CFRP under long-term thermal exposure condition. The results presented here show that the NHC and OHC strength of the polycyanate CFRP did not decline at 180 °C and 195 °C up to 1000 hours. On

the other hand, the OHT strength after thermal exposure for 1800 hours at 180 °C declined slightly. From these results, the polycyanate CFRP would have advantage in usage under the thermo-oxidative environment. Microscopic image of OHT specimen after tests shows that there were a lot of transverse cracks which did not appeared in the 90 ° layers of the non-aged specimens. Thermo-oxidative degradation in long-term exposure causes matrix crack in 90° layer. However crack has little effect on strength and young's modulus for NHC, OHC and OHT test in 1000 or 1800 hours exposure.

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